

EFFECT OF JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE JOB PERFORMANCE MEDIATED BY AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

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Abstract

Job satisfaction is one of the goals to be achieved by organizations. This goal is to support the desire of employees to work better and can have a strong commitment to completing their duties. This study investigates the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance mediated by affective commitment. The survey method used in answering research formulations. Non-parametric suppressors with Partial Least Square (PLS) are used to prove the purpose of the study. The survey conducted at one government office in the city of Bandung by distributing questionnaires to 70 employees. The results showed that the affective commitment of employees could improve the completion of their tasks better. This factor will encourage them to work harder. With the satisfaction of employees who fulfilled driven by a high commitment to the organization will lead to high employee task performance.

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INTRODUCTION

The challenges facing every organization today are focused on serving the needs of the community that are oriented not only to satisfy but more value-oriented. Based on this paradigm, if an organization wants to remain superior, it must be able to respond more quickly to changes or demands of society. (Rice & Mathews, 2014) Rapid response from organizations to changes in the needs or demands of the community requires answers, can be in the form of new product innovations, process innovations, and service quality improvement, which strictly correlated with organizational goals and community interests. Consequently, organizations need human resources who have the expertise and high competencies which also make one of the factors that play a role in increasing the productivity of an organization or agency's performance. (Campbell & Im, 2016)

Human resource development is

carried out in order to provide results that are following the goals and objectives of the organization, with established workability standards. Workability is the mastery of science and technology and the skills that support the smoothness and ease of doing work and can support any changes made by management. (Moynihan & Pandey, 2007) One way to improve employee performance can be through job satisfaction. (Bowman, West, Berman & Van Wart, 2016) Job satisfaction is an emotional state and the attitude of employees towards their work which usually based on whether or not the meeting point occurs between the value of employee work compensation from the organization with the level of service reward desired by the employee. (Liu, Tang & Yang, 2015).

Improving the performance of individual employees has the potential to be able to improve the performance of groups of employees and to improve the

performance of all groups of employees will encourage increased organizational performance that will contribute to accelerating the achievement of goals and objectives set by the organization. Perry (1997) and Bowman, West, Berman & Van Wart (2016) state that employees who are highly committed to the organization will lead to high organizational performance, reduced absenteeism, employee loyalty, and others. Human resources are the most critical investment that can be made by organizations whose ultimate goal boils down to one point, namely that the organization has a quality workforce, good work discipline, highly motivated, committed to the organization, efficiency in all aspects and has work productivity in accordance with the needs of the organization, both for the present and in the future. (Van Scotter, 2000) In government organizations efforts to improve the quality or competence of human resources, especially in terms of the quality of community service has been done. (Campbell & Im, 2016)

Commitment to the organization discusses the closeness of employees to the organization where they are, and at the same time, commitment reflects the strength of employee involvement and loyalty to the organization. (Meyer & Allen, 1991) High commitment to the organization will have a professional attitude and uphold the values that have agreed upon in the organization. (Caillier, 2015). Past research, as well as recent research, support the effect of organizational commitment on desired outcomes, such as performance and negatively affect the desire to move and job absenteeism. (Kuvaas, 2006). In addition to directly related to performance, some opinions explain that organizational commitment is also related to job satisfaction. (Markovits, Davis, Fay & Dick,

2010).

Research conducted by Kim, Ra, Park & Kwon (2017) proves that job satisfaction can increase task performance. Then research conducted by Caillier (2015) proved that commitment can improve prosocial behavior in federal government employees in the United States. Similarly, research conducted by Shim & Faerman (2017) shows that commitment can improve public employees' organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). However, their research uses public service motivation (PSM) as a variable to measure commitment, nor does it measure employee satisfaction. Based on these reasons, this study tries to fill the research model using affective commitment as mediation. Therefore the purpose and objectives of the study are to determine the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance with affective commitment as a mediating variable.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses survey method. The sample respondents were 70 employees at one of the government offices in Bandung. The sampling technique is by simple random sampling where the sample takes randomly.

The variable in this study is job satisfaction measured using the Job Description Index (JDI) scale developed by Balzer et al., (1997) and has validated by Stanton et al., (2002). The affective commitment variable functions as a mediating variable measured using a scale developed by Mayer & Allen (1991). Performance functions as a dependent variable (Dependent variable) which then given a Y notation. As measured by aspects of Job Performance, such as the Implementation of Main Tasks,

Implementation of Additional Tasks and Timeliness of daily report submission.

Measure the research instrument. A validity test performed which illustrates how the questionnaire was able to measure what was to be measured. Then testing reliability is the level of confidence in the results of a measurement. Measurements that have high reliability are measurements that can provide reliable measurement results (reliable). After the test conducted, the analytical technique used was path analysis using a nonparametric approach, namely Partial Least Squares (PLS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of respondents based on age between 31 - 35 years old as many as 3 people or 3.00%, aged between 36-40 years as much as 3.00%, aged between 41 - 45 years as much as 5.00%, aged between 46 - 50 years as many as 23.00% and aged over 50 years as much as 50.00% who are the majority respondents. Based on the general education level of respondents as much as 50.00%, high school education or Diploma as much as 6.00%, Strata 1 as much as 33.00% and Strata 2 as much as 11.00%. Thus respondents with a high school education are the majority of respondents. Based on data from Men as much as 52.00% while Women as much as 42.00%. Thus women are fewer than men. Profile of respondents based on group III as much as 88.00% while group IV as much as 12.00%. Thus group III is the most dominant respondent.

Validity and reliability

Table 1. Result of Outer Loading Indicator

Outer Loading	Satis	Comm	Perform
sat1	0.850		
sat2	0.830		
sat3	0.751		
sat4	0.784		

sat5	0.770		
sat6	0.867		
sat7	0.670		
sat8	0.808		
sat9	0.656		
sat10	0.702		
sat11	0.813		
sat12	0.757		
sat13	0.831		
sat14	0.846		
sat15	0.693		
com1		0.617	
com2		0.831	
com3		0.833	
com4		0.852	
com5		0.717	
com6		0.795	
com7		0.836	
com8		0.692	
Per1			0.850
Per2			0.821
Per3			0.663
Per4			0.619

Based on table 1, it is known that satisfaction indicators 1 - 15 have values above 0.5, indicator Affective commitment 1 - 8 have values above 0.5, and task performance indicators 1-4 above values 0.5. All indicators are declared valid because they are above the required value.

Table 2. Result of Reliabilities

Variables	CA	rho_A	CR	AVE
CommAff	0.903	0.908	0.923	0.602
Performance	0.728	0.753	0.831	0.555
Satisfaction	0.953	0.955	0.958	0.605

Table 2 presents the results of reliability calculations based on Cronbach's Alpha, rho_A, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The criteria used to refer to Hair (2014) where the value of Cronbach's Alpha, rho_A, Composite Reliability > 0.7 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.5.

The calculation results show that the values of Cronbach's Alpha, rho_A, Composite Reliability, and Average

Variance Extracted (AVE) have met the specified requirements. Likewise, the value of Discriminant Validity which refers to the Fornell-Larcker criteria, as seen in table 3, shows that the correlation value between variables is higher than other variables.

Table 3. Result of Discriminant Validity

Fornell-Larcker	CommAff	Performance	Satisfaction
CommAff	0.776		
Performance	0.757	0.745	
Satisfaction	0.770	0.704	0.778

Table 5. Result of Path Coefficients and significant.

Path	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
CommAff -> Perform	0.529	0.126	3.626	0.000
Satisfaction-> CommAff	0.770	0.060	12.595	0.000
Satisfaction-> Perform	0.296	0.138	2.569	0.000

Table 5 illustrates that the path coefficient indicates it supported by calculations where the p-value indicates a significant value. In general, the research model can illustrate in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Path Analysis

Based on the explanation above, it appears that the satisfaction variable on performance has an effect of 0.296, the effect of satisfaction on the affective commitment of 0.770, and the effect of affective commitment on the performance of 0.529. Overall the R2 value of 0.609 shows that there are other influences outside the model studied.

The results of the research are generally good; it can see from the dimensions of affective commitment that are good enough. It can see from the involvement of employees who are already good enough. Where the employees play an active role and try to be involved in every event held by agencies other than that, employees also look critical in building their institutions where every shortcoming always tries to be criticized wisely by every employee.

From the results of research and data processing task performance is in the category of sufficient. The performance measurement of the tasks used in the study is aspects of work performance: the implementation of the main tasks, the implementation of additional tasks, the timeliness of delivering daily reports. In general, the performance are good enough; it can see that the employees' fluency is quite good, although there are still some employees who appear to be absent.

The level of employee discipline where employees rarely leave before hours goes home as well as the present where in general employees always give news if the employee is absent from work, the implementation of duties and responsibilities have been going well.

The implementation of the main tasks has been carried out by the employees

quite well as for the implementation of additional tasks which are generally carried out by the employees quite well, as well as submission of tasks and reports of work results that are good enough.

According to Porter, Steers, Mowday & Boulian (1974) argues that organizational performance influenced by the level of involvement and commitment of people to their duties. This factor will encourage them to work harder. (Meyer, 2015) This factor will make HR work better. This study supports previous research which proves that there is an influence of satisfaction and commitment on employee performance such as Chen, Lin & Wu (2016); Caillier (2015); De Gieter & Hofmans (2015); De Gieter, Hofmans & Bakker (2018) Hadian (2017); Hardiyana, Yusup & Sidharta (2015); Ra, Park & Kwon (2017); Shim & Faerman (2017); and Yousef (2017).

The results of this study indicate that the affective commitment of employees can improve the completion of their tasks better. This factor will encourage them to work harder. With the satisfaction of employees who fulfilled driven by a high commitment to the organization will lead to high employee task performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The level of employee affective commitment will create a professional work climate, as indicated by an increase in task performance. Similarly, job satisfaction can encourage the affective commitment of employees in improving their performance. The results showed that job satisfaction and driven by affective commitment can improve performance. Therefore the success of an organization's management is very

much determined by its success in managing its human resources. A high or low commitment of employees to the organization where they work is crucial to determine the performance to be achieved by the organization — likewise, employee job satisfaction.

Research has limitations which only measure the affective commitment of employees, while normative commitment and continuous commitment not examined in this study. It expected that in future studies, it could measure normative or continuous commitment which has implications for the performance of the officer.

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